

Thermogravimetric study of Thallium-Thorium Double Carbonate

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The thermolysis of thallium-thorium double carbonate, commonly referred to as thallium penta-carbonato thorate $Tl[Th(CO_3)_5] \cdot 2H_2O$ has been studied upto 1200° . It is concluded that (i) only two carbonate groups are attached to the thorium ion and not all the five; (ii) the two water molecules are also attached to the thorium, thereby completing the six-coordination of thorium, (iii) the remaining three carbonate groups are attached to the thallium, (iv) the crystalline compound is not a true complex compound (penta-carbonato thorate) but a double carbonate, where three moles of the monovalent metal carbonate and one of the hydrated thorium carbonate are bonded together possibly through hydrogen bonds, and (v) the formula is best represented as

In continuation of our studies on the mono-valent metal-thorium carbonates of, the general formula $M_6^+ Th(CO_3)_5 \cdot nH_2O$, the results of a thermogravimetric study upto $1200^\circ C$ of $Tl_6 Th(CO_3)_5 \cdot 2H_2O$ are reported. For comparison the thermolysis of pure Tl_2CO_3 has also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation :

$Tl_6 \cdot Th(CO_3)_5 \cdot 2H_2O$ was prepared following the method of Charnyaev, Golonya and Molodkin¹ using $TlNO_3$ (E. Merck, G. R. grade), $Th(NO_3)_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ (Indian Rare Earths Ltd.—nuclear grade) and $(NH_4)_2CO_3$ (BDH, Analar). The compound was obtained as a white, microcrystalline powder which gave a sharp X-ray pattern. (Reqd.: $Tl-68.4\%$, $Th-12.9\%$, $CO_3-16.7\%$ and $H_2O-2.0\%$; found: $Tl-68.0\%$, $Th-12.9\%$, $CO_3-16.6\%$ and $H_2O-2.0\%$). It is pertinent to note that when L.R. grade $TlNO_3$ was used, the compound obtained was amorphous and no X-ray diffraction pattern could be recorded. The reason for this behaviour is not clear.

Tl_2CO_3 was prepared by mixing hot 5% solutions of $TlNO_3$ and $(NH_4)_2CO_3$ cooling to room temperature and then precipitating the Tl_2CO_3 by addition of acetone. The precipitate was filtered and washed with acetone.

Chemical Analysis :

Thorium. The compound was dissolved in dil. HNO_3 and thorium was estimated as ThO_2 using the hydroxide method². In order to maintain thallium in the thallos state, SO_2 was bubbled before addition of NH_4OH to precipitate the thorium hydroxide.

1. I. I. Chernyaev, V. A. Golonya and A. K. Modolkin, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1961, **6**, 394 (English translation, p. 200).
2. C. J. Rodden "Analytical Chemistry of the Manhattan Project", p. 183, McGraw Hill, New York (1950).

Thallium was estimated in the filtrate. Both the oxide³ (Tl_2O_3) and chromate⁴ (Tl_2CrO_4) methods were used. The latter method gave very much better results.

Carbonate was estimated following standard procedures by adsorption of CO_2 on ascarite traps⁵. The results were also confirmed from thermogravimetric measurements.

Water was estimated by decomposing the compound in vacuum at about 120° and absorbing the vapours on $Mg(ClO_4)_2$ traps. The results were confirmed from thermogravimetric measurements.

X-ray Powder Analysis. X-ray diffractometric patterns were recorded using the Philips Wide Angle Goniometer and filtered CuK_α radiation from the Philips PW 1010 fully stabilized X-ray generator. The d -spacings of the double carbonate which are reported for the first time and that of the simple Tl_2CO_3 are given in Tables I and II respectively. The values for the latter compound are given since certain discrepancies have been noted in comparison with the pattern obtained photographically and given in the ASTM card index.

TABLE I

Partial X-ray data of $Tl_6Th(CO_3)_5 \cdot 2H_2O$.

$d(\text{\AA})$	I/I_0
3.98	41
3.88	79
3.30	94
3.14	97
2.95	57
2.78	9
2.68	100
2.57	8
2.45	29
2.37	6
2.20	18
2.15	17
2.10	9
2.02	52
1.98	33
1.95	7
1.94	36
1.92	10
1.88	26
1.85	64
1.77	6
1.67	15
1.64	17
1.62	14
1.59	15
1.57	14

3. F. D. Treadwell and W. T. Hall "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II, p. 53. Wiley, New York (1947).
4. A. I. Vogel "Text book of Quantitative Inorganic Chemistry", p. 477 Longman (1948).
5. W. F. Hillerbrand and G. E. F. Lundell, "Applied Inorganic Analysis", p. 768, J. Wiley and Sons (1948).

TABLE II

Comparison of the diffractometric X-ray data of Tl_2CO_3 (Prepared) and Tl_2CO_3 (J. Matthey) with that of Tl_2CO_3 (ASTM)

Tl_2CO_3 (Prep.)		Tl_2CO_3 (J.Matthey)		Tl_2CO_3 (ASTM)	
$d(\text{\AA})$	I/I_0	$d(\text{\AA})$	I/I_0	$d(\text{\AA})$	I/I_0
—	—	—	—	5.57	5
—	—	—	—	4.85	5
—	—	—	—	4.41	80
4.36	46	4.36	18	—	—
4.02	9	—	—	—	—
—	—	—	—	4.00	30
3.89	7	—	—	—	—
3.73	25	3.74	29	—	—
3.62	7	—	—	—	—
3.43	100	3.44	63	—	—
—	—	—	—	3.30	20
3.28	98	3.28	46	—	—
3.17	76	3.17	100	—	—
—	—	—	—	3.14	20
3.08	25	3.08	27	3.07	30
—	—	—	—	2.97	100
2.94	46	2.94	26	—	—
2.90	57	2.89	46	—	—
—	—	—	—	2.76	5
2.668	46	2.69	15	—	—
2.63	52	2.63	47	—	—
—	—	2.48	26	2.462	20
—	—	—	—	2.450	30
2.39	13	2.39	10	—	—
2.30	28	2.30	34	—	—
2.26	24	2.26	17	2.196	20
2.18	12	2.18	7	—	—
2.08	6	2.08	12	—	—
2.07	5	2.07	13	—	—
2.05	14	2.05	15	—	—
—	—	2.03	10	—	—
2.02	4	2.02	9	—	—
—	—	—	—	2.001	10

Additional lines were also observed

Thermogravimetric Analysis. Thermolysis of the compound was studied on a Stanton thermobalance (high temperature model, 1 mg sensitivity). The T. G. curve and the D. T. G plot obtained therefrom are shown in figures 1 to 4 for the double and the simple carbonates. The results are tabulated in Tables III and IV.

TABLE III

Thermal decomposition of thalious carbonate

Substance		: Tl_2CO_3		Wt. taken		: 1.001 g.		
Chart speed		: 6"/hr.		Rate of heating		: 6°C/min.		
Step No.	Temp. °C		Loss in mgs.		% Loss		Evolving Species	Reaction
	Starting	Ending	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Theor.		
I	335	445	i)	94.1		i)	9.41	i) $Tl_2CO_3 \rightarrow Tl_2O + CO_2$
				(due to loss of CO_2)				
			ii)	68.3		ii)	6.83	ii) $Tl_2O + O_2 \rightarrow Tl_2O_3$
				(gain due to intake of O_2)				
			26 (overall)	25.7 (overall)	2.6 (net %)	2.57 (net %)	$Tl_2CO_3 + O_2 \rightarrow Tl_2O_3 + CO_2$	
II	580	950	975	974.3	97.4	97.4	Tl_2O_3	Complete loss of Tl_2O_3 by complex reaction. Final residue : Nil.

TABLE IV

Thermal decomposition of thallium thorium compound

Substance : $Tl_6Th(CO_3)_5 \cdot 2H_2O$ Wt. taken : 1.00 gms.
 Chart speed : 6"/hr. Rate of Heating : 6°C/min.

Step No.	Temp. °C		Loss in mgs.		% Loss		Evolving Species	Reaction
	Starting	Ending	Obs.	Cal.	Obs.	Theor.		
I	50	180	20	20.06	2.0	2.01	$2H_2O$	$3Tl_2CO_3 \cdot Th(CO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O \rightarrow 3Tl_2CO_3 \cdot Th(CO_3)_2 + 2H_2O \uparrow$
II	180	380	49	49.05	4.9	4.905	$2CO_2$	$3Tl_2CO_3 \cdot Th(CO_3)_2 \rightarrow 3Tl_2CO_3 + ThO_2 + 2CO_2 \uparrow$
III	380	510	21	73.63	7.5	7.363	$3CO_2$	i) $3Tl_2CO_3 + ThO_2 \rightarrow 3Tl_2O + ThO_2 + 3CO_2$
			(+54 Oxid.)					
			= 75 (net)					$3Tl_2CO_3 + 3O_2 + ThO_2 \rightarrow 3Tl_2O_3 + ThO_2 + 3CO_2 \uparrow$
IV	610	1200	742	763.8	74.2	76.4	$3Tl_2O_3$	$3Tl_2O_3 \rightarrow$ volatilization (Complex reaction)

Final residue : ThO_2 + small amount of unvolatilized Tl_2O_3
 (ThO_2 lines confirmed by X-rays).

DISCUSSION

Water of crystallisation. Rosenhein⁶, who was the first to synthesize the thallium-thorium carbonate in 1903, reported that the compound was isolated in an anhydrous state. Chernyaev, et al¹ found by chemical analysis that the thallium derivative contained a little more than one molecule of water, while all the other complexes prepared by them contained three or more moles of water. Unlike previously reported^{1,6} the compound is obtained invariably with two moles of water.

In case of compounds with other mono valent metal ions⁷, the number of water molecules has sometimes been greater than 2, when $(n-2)$ moles are lost initially and the other 2 moles are lost in the range 170 to 220°. From this it is concluded that two molecules of water are directly bonded to the thorium ion and constitute the water of coordination, the remaining water molecules if any, constitute the water of crystallisation.

Carbonate complex. Chernyaev *et al.*¹ have presumed that one water molecule is directly attached to the thorium and this together with the five monodenting carbonate groups constitute the hexa-coordination $[\text{Th}(\text{CO}_3)_5 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]^{6-}$. Faucherra and Dervin⁸ from cryoscopic measurements gave the formula $[\text{Th}(\text{CO}_3)_5]^{6-}$, identical with that supposed to exist in the solid state and subsequently confirmed it by a potentiometric study⁹. In 1963, Ryabchikov *et al.*¹⁰ from hi-frequency titration studies proposed that the structural formula of these complexes should be $\text{M}_4^{+}[\text{Th}(\text{CO}_3)_4]$. $\text{M}_2^{+}\text{CO}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where $\text{M}^{+} = \text{Na}^{+}$ or K^{+}). Karyakin and Volynets¹¹ from an infra-red study supported this formula on the ground that they observed infra-red absorption due to both the ionic and the coordinated type of carbonate groups. In these formulations thorium is assumed to have either 5, 6, 8 or 10 coordinations, even though the most common one is the six coordination.

To ascertain the nature of the compound thermogravimetric analysis was undertaken,

From the observed weight losses (Table III) it is evident that only two moles of CO_2 are lost between 180–350°, immediately following the loss of two moles of H_2O . The remaining three moles are expelled at higher temperatures accompanied by the simultaneous oxidation of Tl_2O formed, to Tl_2O_3 . These facts are clearly brought out in the D.T.G. plot (fig. 2).

Fig 1
TRACING OF T.G. CURVE OF $\text{Tl}_5\text{Th}(\text{CO}_3)_5 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

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8. J. Faucherra and J. Dervin, *Comp. Rend.*, 1962, **255**, 2264.
9. *Idem.*, *ibid.*, 1962, **255**, 2769.
10. D. I. Ryabchikov, M. P. Volynets, V. A. Zarinskii and V. I. Ivanov, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1963, **18**, 348. *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, **58**, 13403.

The D.T.G. peak for the loss of these three moles of CO_2 occurs at 425° (fig. 2), while that observed in the pure Th_2CO_3 occurs at 435° (fig. 3-4). This finer resolution of the peaks is not obvious in the normal T.G. curve and demonstrates the need of constructing D.T.G. plots.

Fig 2
D T G CURVE OF $\text{Th}_6\text{Th}(\text{CO}_3)_5 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

It is therefore concluded that out of the five carbonate groups present, the two which are lost immediately following dehydration are directly attached to the thorium ion. From the number of carbonate and H_2O groups attached to the thorium ion, it is presumed that the carbonate groups are bidentate and not monodentate as presumed by other workers.

These bidentate CO_3 groups can be expected to occupy the square base, while the oxygen from the two water molecules constitute the two apexes of the octahedra. The remaining three CO_3 would be attached to the monovalent metal ion, essentially as in the corresponding normal carbonates and could be loosely bonded to the neutral complex by means of hydrogen bonds.

Fig 3
TRACING OF T, G CURVE OF Th_2CO_3

Such a structure would not be inconsistent with the observations of Karyakin and Volynets¹¹, since the infra-red absorption would show as observed by them, both the ionic and the coordinated carbonate groups. For obtaining evidence for the existence of bidentate or monodentate coordinated carbonate groups we have undertaken a separate infra-red study of these carbonates.

FIG 4 D T G CURVE OF Tl_2CO_3

Loss of thallic oxide : The product left after the loss of the residual three CO_2 is a mixture of Tl_2O_3 and ThO_2 as confirmed by X-ray diffractometric analysis. On further heating the Tl_2O_3 is lost, exhibiting three peaks in the D.T.G. plot. In the end essentially pure ThO_2 remains. The loss of thallic oxide occurs by a series of reactions which will form the subject matter of subsequent communication¹².

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